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THE COVERAGE WIDTH OF THE COMPREHENSIVE FLAT-CUTTER WORKING BODY FOR INTENSIVE GARDEN INTER-ROW PROCESSING ITS EFFECT ON PERFORMANCE

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Annotation. In this article, the results of the study of the effect of the coverage width of the working body of a comprehensive flat-cutter, which completely cuts the weeds in the intensive garden rows, and quality treatment of the soil between the garden rows, on its performance are presented. In this, it was determined that the coverage width of the comprehensive flat cutting tool should be 75 cm. The tests were conducted in an intensive drip-irrigated orchard planted in a 4x1.2 scheme.

Keywords. Intensive garden, cultivator, extensive flat-cutter body, spherical disc, soil pusher leveler, weed.

ШИРИНА ЗАХВАТА ВСЕСТОРОННИЙ ПЛОСКОРЕЖУЩЕГО РАБОЧЕГО ОРГАНА ДЛЯ ИНТЕНСИВНОЙ МЕЖДУРЯДНОЙ ОБРАБОТКИ САДА ВЛИЯЕТ НА ПРОИЗВОДИТЕЛЬНОСТЬ

Аннотация. В данной статье приведены результаты исследования влияния ширины захвата рабочего органа комплексной плоскорезки, полностью подрезающей сорняки в интенсивных рядах, и качественной

обработки почвы между междурядьями. представлены его результаты. При этом было установлено, что ширина охвата комплексного плоскорезущего инструмента должна составлять 75 см. Испытания проводились в саду интенсивного капельного орошения, посаженном по схеме 4x1,2.

Ключевые слова. Интенсивный сад, культиватор, удлиненный плоскорезущий корпус, сферический диск, разравниватель почвы, прополка.

Introduction. In recent years, large-scale work has been carried out in our republic on the effective use of agricultural land, the volume of intensive garden areas has been expanded, and the cultivation of the soil between garden rows with combined implements has been widely introduced. Because in order to get a high yield from intensive orchards, it is necessary to carry out seasonal agrotechnical activities on time and with high quality. Implementation of advanced technologies and experiences in garden care, fighting against various diseases in a prescribed manner allows to get a high yield from gardens. Cleaning the land from weeds is of great importance in softening the soil surface. Cultivation is carried out with the help of a cultivator to remove weeds and break up the clumps and loosen compacted soil without overturning. Today, existing aggregates or their adapted options are used in intensive garden inter-row cultivation with drip irrigation. This situation leads to an increase in labor costs for the production of products in drip-irrigated intensive gardens and an increase in operations for the implementation of agrotechnical processes performed in the care of the garden, and this, in turn, has a negative effect on the productivity of gardens. In horticulture, the increase in the number of machine operations during inter-row cultivation leads to the destruction of the soil structure, increasing its hardness and density, as a result, it negatively affects the development of the root system of seedlings. The main reason for this is that the structural and technological parameters of the machines used in drip-irrigated intensive gardens do not match the operating conditions. In order to overcome the above-mentioned shortcomings, it is an important task to develop an

energy- and resource-efficient soil tillage system for intensive garden row cultivation [1].

Materials and methods. In the research process, theoretical mechanics, agricultural mechanics, higher mathematics, mathematical planning of experiments and tensometry, as well as the methods specified in the existing regulatory documents: O’z DSt 3236:2017, O’z DSt 3412:2019, GOST 20915-2011 and other regulatory documents used. Based on the results of theoretical studies, the Agricultural Mechanization Scientific Research Institute was created a prototype of a machine that works intensively between garden rows and buries exposed tree roots. (Figure 1).

1-frame equipped with a suspension device; 2-5-front and back row flat-cutter working bodies; 3-spherical disk; 4-soil pusher leveler; 6-base wheel.

Figure 1. Intensive garden tillage between the rows construction scheme of the cultivator.

The proposed machine consists of a frame (1) equipped with a suspension device, extensive flat-cutting working bodies (2,5), a spherical disk (3), a soil pusher leveler (5) and a support wheel (6)

(1-picture). The technological process of the machine is as follows: A wide range of flat cutters for garden inter-row cutting, weeding and quality inter-row management. Spherical discs cut a layer of soil from outside the protection zone,

lift it along the work surface and throw it to the side, burying the exposed roots of trees, and the soil pusher leveler smoothes the unevenness formed on the surface of the soil thrown from the side of the spherical disc, and it is used by the tree. pushes to the bottom. [3; 4].

Before conducting field experiments, the degree of weed infestation and the mechanical composition of the soil between intensive garden rows were studied according to GOST 20915-2011 [2]. Based on the results obtained in theoretical

studies, wide-ranging flat-cutting working bodies with the opening angle of the working body $2\gamma_i = 90^\circ$, its coverage widths $B_i = 55, 65, 75, 85$ cm were prepared (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Coverage width a-55 cm; b-65 cm; c-75 cm; d-85 cm comprehensive flat-cutting working bodies

In experimental studies, the coverage width of the flat cutting tool and the angle of the blade of the tool into the soil, the width of the blade of the tool and its angle of crushing the soil, the arrangement of the tools in the frame, the level of cutting weeds between the garden rows, and the depth of cultivation, the impact of the working body on the traction resistance and the level of soil compaction was studied.

Analysis of research results.

In the conducted experiments, the opening angle of the wide-ranging flat-cutting working body $2\gamma_i = 90^\circ$, its coverage widths $B_i = 55, 65, 75$ and 85 cm were carried out at speeds of 5.0 and 7.0 km/h. In this case, the angle of entry of the blades of the flat cutter into the soil was set at $b_p = 25^\circ$, the length of the blade of the flat cutter was 21 cm, the width of the blade was $b_i = 8$ cm, and its angle of entry into the soil was set at $a_i = 30^\circ$. The obtained results are presented in Figure 3.

a) b)
s) d)

1 and 2 - when the aggregate speed is 5.0 and 7.0 km/h, respectively

Figure 3. Graphs of the coverage width of the wide flat cutter as a function of weed loss rate (a), tillage depth (b), traction resistance (c) and soil compaction (d)

As can be seen from the graph above, the level of weed cutting and the level

of soil compaction increased when the width of the flat cutting working body increased from 55 cm to 85 cm. These indicators increased at speeds of 5.0 and 7.0 km/h of the unit, respectively. As the width of the flat cutter blade increases, the drag resistance increases accordingly. Because as the width of the working body of the flat cutter increases, the surface of the soil affected by it also increases, and as a result, the traction resistance increases accordingly. When the coverage width is 85 cm, the unit's tensile strength exceeded the specified standard, which had a negative effect on its energy performance. When the speed increased from 5.0 km/h to 7.0 km/h, the quality of soil compaction improved a little, that is, with the

increase in speed, the impact force applied to the soil by the working body increased, and as a result, the compaction of the soil improved, and on the contrary, when the speed increased to 5 The depth of processing at a speed of 0.0 km/h was higher than that at a speed of 7.0 km/h. Because when the speed of the unit increases, we can see that the depth of penetration of the working body into the soil is significantly reduced due to the speed.

Conclusions.

Based on the above analysis, the rate of weed loss between intensive garden rows is directly dependent on the coverage width of the flat cutter, and it is desirable that its coverage width be at least 75 cm.

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